

The Nature of Culture

Program and Abstracts

ROCEEH Symposium

June 15-18, 2011

Tübingen, Germany

EBERHARD KARLS
UNIVERSITÄT
TÜBINGEN

SENCKENBERG
world of biodiversity

THE ROLE
OF CULTURE
IN EARLY
EXPANSIONS
OF HUMANS

Supported by Deutsche
Forschungsgemeinschaft

**HEIDELBERGER AKADEMIE
DER WISSENSCHAFTEN**

Akademie der Wissenschaften des
Landes Baden-Württemberg

THE ROLE
OF CULTURE
IN EARLY
EXPANSIONS
OF HUMANS

Symposium
June 15-18, 2011
Tübingen, Germany

The Nature of Culture

Program and Abstracts

HEIDELBERGER AKADEMIE
DER WISSENSCHAFTEN

Akademie der Wissenschaften des Landes Baden-Württemberg

EBERHARD KARLS
UNIVERSITÄT
TÜBINGEN

SENCKENBERG
world of biodiversity

Supported by Deutsche
Forschungsgemeinschaft

DFG Deutsche
Forschungsgemeinschaft

Location of the symposium

Schloss Hohentübingen
Fürstenzimmer
Burgsteige 11
72070 Tübingen

Conference office

Chidi Nwokeji
Chidi.Nwokeji@senckenberg.de
Mobil: 0176-48 20 64 52

Hotel

Hotel Am Schloss
Burgsteige 18
72070 Tübingen
Tel: +49 (0)7071 92940
www.hotelamschloss.de

Restaurant

Weinstube Forelle
Kronenstraße 8
72070 Tübingen
Tel: +49 (0) 70 71 - 2 40 94

- (A) Train station
- (B) Hotel
- (C) Location of the Symposium
- (D) Restaurant Forelle

Program

Each talk of 40 min is followed by 20 min for questions and discussion.

Wednesday, 15/06/2011 – Traditions, basic culture and beyond: The expansion of cultural capacity in early human evolution

8:00 Registration

9:00 Welcome

9:30 Miriam Haidle, Frankfurt: A model of expansion of cultural capacity – An introduction

10:30 *Coffee break*

11:00 Andrew Whiten, St. Andrews: The critical pre-hominin foundations of hominin cultural evolution

12:00 Iain Davidson, Armidale: Stone tools–evidence of something in between culture and cumulative culture?

13:00 *Lunch break*

14:00 Anne Delagnes, Bordeaux: The nature of the earliest hominin cultures

15:00 Discussion: Is it possible to differentiate between basic culture and delayed culture?

16:00 *Coffee break, visit to the Museum Schloss Hohentübingen*

18:00 Evening lecture by Nicholas J. Conard, Tübingen: The nature of culture–evidence from cave sites of the Swabian Jura

19:00 *Reception*

Thursday, 16/06/2011 –Cumulative culture and beyond?

8:30 Claudio Tennie, David Braun & Shannon MacPherron, Leipzig: Cumulative culture—cognitive and social prerequisites and possible material outcomes

9:30 Nira Alperson-Afil & Naama Goren-Inbar: Scarce but significant: The limestone component of the Acheulian site of Gesher Benot Ya'aqov, Israel

10:30 *Coffee break*

11:00 Marlize Lombard, Johannesburg: Is increasing technological, behavioural and cognitive flexibility an effect of cumulative culture? Stone Age hunting weapons as proxy for the evolution of human flexibility

12:00 April Nowell, Victoria: The evolution of play and its role in the extension of cultural competence

13:00 *Lunch break*

14:00 Lyn Wadley, Johannesburg: The relationship between technological, cognitive and cultural complexity

15:00 Discussion: How can cumulative culture be traced in the archaeological record?

16:00 *Coffee break*

16:30 Stephen Shennan, London: Demography and cultural identity

17:30 Thorsten Uthmeier, Erlangen: Cultural identity in Neanderthals?

19.30 *Conference Dinner at the restaurant "Forelle"*

Friday, 17/06/2011 – Material evidence of cultural capacity

- Excursion to Hohle Fels and Geißenklösterle, two cave sites in the Ach Valley near Blaubeuren
- Visit to the Urgeschichtliches Museum Blaubeuren
- Michael Bolus, Tübingen: Tracing cultural identity in Early Upper Palaeolithic stone and organic tools
- Discussion: Communal culture vs. cultural modernity – a comparison of the material evidence of the two concepts regarding cultural capacity and cultural performances

Saturday, 18/06/2011 – Communal culture, and how cultural can culture be?

9:00 Marian Vanhaeren, Nanterre: Aurignacian evidence—culture defining identity, culture giving identity

10:00 James O’Connell, Salt Lake City: A view from behavioral ecology: How cultural is culture?

11:00 *Coffee break*

11:30 Don Gardner, Luzern: Critical remarks on the model of expansion of cultural capacity from a cultural anthropologist’s perspective

12:30 *Lunch break*

13:30 Final discussion: In-depth examination of the complete model of expansion of cultural capacity

16:00 *End of the symposium*

Expansions of Cultural Capacity

Miriam Noël Haidle

Research Institute Senckenberg, The Role of Culture in Early Expansions of Humans, Frankfurt

Mostly regarded as a uniquely human concept, the term culture has been applied in the last decades also to specific behavioral patterns of animals (e.g. Rendell & Whitehead 2001; van Schaik et al. 2003; Whiten et al. 1999). However, the meaning of the term “culture” is quite diverse in the different fields of application. Multiple definitions are in use in the social and cultural sciences (Kroeber & Kluckhohn 1952; Hammel 2007) referring only to cultural expressions of modern human societies, while other definitions are used to trace animal culture with emphasis on the social transmission of information in contrast to genetic inheritance. The two lines of approaches are reflected in the culturalistic and naturalistic views on culture in philosophy. Culturalism emphasizes humans (generally *Homo sapiens*) as intentionally and purposefully acting cultural beings and cultural achievements as meaningful and self-determined; an evolutionary perspective is mainly lacking. In contrast, naturalism explains cultural achievements like other natural phenomena by natural forces and laws: animals can also be thought of as bearers of culture with a development of culture being driven by evolution. In between of these extreme positions, paleoanthropology and Paleolithic archeology are studying the evolution of hominins and of cultural expressions in the genus *Homo* in order to gain a clearer picture about the course of development and the causes of changes in “culture”.

The archaeological record of the Paleolithic is very fragmentary and mostly restricted to artifacts made from durable raw material like stone or with some limitations bone, antler, ivory, and teeth. The former existence of artifacts made from more perishable raw material like wood, leather, or even synthetic materials like birch tar or compound adhesives is proven directly by rare finds and indirectly by functional analyses of stone tools. The reconstruction of the behavior at a certain time in

human prehistory is restricted by this limited record. In contrast, the data bases of cultural and social sciences dealing with recent or historic populations as well as of the behavioral study of modern animal species are significantly broader due to direct observations and written records. The reconstruction of Paleolithic behavior is even complicated by the problem to assign the record to a specific hominin species, respectively a population. These constraints distinguish the approaches to “culture” taken by Paleolithic archeology from those of other cultural and social sciences, but also from the ethology of modern animal species. Although the Paleolithic record provides only fragmentary insight, it shows significant changes of the cultural behavior in the course of human evolution clearly exceeding the cultural expressions of animals. To understand the evolution of the biological and cultural being *Homo sapiens*, however, it is counterproductive to simply draw a line between “culture” and “non-culture”. Instead, the nature of culture has to be disclosed and its development has to be decoded.

Several attempts have been made in the last decade to approach the concept of culture from a more integrative point of view, to understand “culture across species” (Byrne et al. 2004) and “the evolution of cultural evolution” (Henrich, J. & R. McElreath 2003), to look for “a unified science of cultural evolution” (Messoudi et al. 2006), and to gain insight in how “culture evolves” (Whiten et al. 2011). In order to give a unified basis to study human cultural evolution, a multi-stage model of the expansion of cultural capacity will be introduced below. First, cultural capacity is described as a product of three dimensions – a biological, a historical, and an individual – with interdependency with the surrounding specific environment (Fig. 1). Second, the model of the course of development of cultural capacity is given in steps of extension (Fig. 2). Third, the concept of cultural performance is introduced as the part of a cultural capacity actually expressed by a specific population (Fig. 3). Biological requirements and the material outcome (possible expressions) of the different steps of cultural capacity are partially and preliminarily compiled in Table 1. The validity of the proposed developmental steps of cultural capacity and possible archaeological evidence that confirms the presence of each individual step will be discussed at the symposium “The nature of culture”.

Cultural capacity within a specific environment

Cultural capacity of an individual as well as of a population or a species possesses three main dimensions of development: a biological, a historical and an individual dimension (Fig. 1) (Haidle 2008a).

Fig. 1 Cultural capacity with three dimensions of development, their main mechanisms and their embedding into the specific environment.

The biological dimension comprises the biological potential and constraints for cultural behavior—in genes, gene expression, anatomy, physiology, and expressed for example in brain structure, sensory perception, motor and articulation skills, sociality, ability to communicate—, with mutation and selection as the principal mechanisms of change. The historical dimensions represents the historical potential and constraints— the set of historically acquired knowledge and skills, the access to these knowledge and skills, the ways and extent of storage, transmission, permutation, and transformation of these knowledge and skills. The principal mechanisms of change on the historical axis are innovation and tradition. The individual dimension gives the individual potential and constraints set by the personal social setting and individual life history of experiences. An additional mechanism of change is effective on this axis: invention. All three dimensions are multi-factorial and not fully independent. Rather, the three dimensions influence one another directly or indirectly via reciprocal effects with each other and with the specific environment (Haidle 2008b). The specific environment is the sum of the cultural and the social environment of an individual, a population or a species plus a section of the natural environment which effects or is affected by the individual, a population or a species. Although being situated in the same landscape, the specific environment of a lion and a *Homo ergaster* differ markedly by the conspecifics, by biotic and abiotic agents effecting and biotic and abiotic objects affected, by the form of relationship with conspecifics/agents/objects, and by the

time depth in past and future direction that influences these relationships, respectively behavior. Fig. 1 provides no more than a rough sketch that accentuates the different developmental lines of cultural capacity—neither a mere biological product, nor solely a historical issue—and their embedding into the specific environment.

A model for the Expansion of Cultural Capacities

Changing biological, historical and individual factors do not produce “culture” in a single creative event, in the sense that if chimpanzees possess culture it is in the same form as modern humans do. Rather, these factors generate different cultural capacities with specific requirements and possibilities of expression. The underlying developmental process is gradual. Nevertheless, some steps of expansion can be identified. Fig. 2 provides a closer view of cultural capacity and the proposed steps of extension.

Fig. 2 The expansion of cultural capacity

The model does not imply a progression of steps, but focuses on an extension of cultural capacity that incorporates the inclusion of achievements from earlier states. Only the two most influential dimensions of development, the biological and historical ones, become visible in this representation. The individual dimension can be neglected in this figure to simplify the model.

Within the model for the expansion of cultural capacity, six steps were identified so far of which provisional definitions are presented below.

- **Socially transmitted information:** Socially transmitted information is a basic cultural factor. In the most simple version, these are instant data with no long-term impact on behavior. Example: waggle dance of bees.

- **Tradition:** Traditions are behavioral patterns that have been transmitted through repeated social learning and have become permanent characteristics of a group. Example: washing of potatoes in a group of Japanese macaques from the islet of Koshima is a famous example, but traditions have also been documented in fish and a number of bird and mammal species. (Galef 2004).

- **Basic culture:** Basic culture consists of a number of traditions that differ between geographical groups. Additionally, these behavioral differences should not be the mere effect of environmental conditions, such as the presence of a specific food source. Though behavior is learned from other individuals, the impulse to adopt features comes from the learner and remains individual. What is learned from others is a general focus on a specific result, but the precise sequence of actions is of secondary interest. This form of culture is restricted to a limited number of single behavioral patterns. Example: Regarding animals today, at least chimpanzees and orangutans fulfill the prerequisites; the same can also be assumed for early Homo species and probably for some Australopithecines. (Rendell & Whitehead 2001; van Schaik et al. 2003; Whiten 2009; Whiten et al. 1999).

- **Delayed culture:** In delayed culture not only are immediate objectives set, but culturally induced aims can be achieved indirectly, with a temporal gap and a discontinuity in action. Problems can be divided into several subordinate goals. The delay of solutions broadens the spectrum of problems that can be approached with cultural behavior. The mechanisms of social transmission are the same as in basic culture. Example: Producers of early stone tools. (Davidson & McGrew 2005; Delagnes & Roche 2005; Goren-Inbar 2011; Haidle 2010; McPherron et al. 2010; Roche et al. 1999; Sharon et al. 2011; Whiten et al. 2009).

- **Cumulative culture:** In cumulative culture changes are built upon one another and accumulate over time. Problems need not be solved again and again from scratch. Rather, already available solutions that are not fully fitting can be adapted or further developed, comparable to a ratchet. Cumulative culture is intimately connected with special forms of social learning—process oriented imitation and active teaching—both of which require an understanding of the “other” as an intentional actor. The behavioral and material products of cumulative culture, however, are limited to individual objectives and use. Example: The typical focus on processes instead of results is archaeologically detectable in the artifacts of *Homo heidelbergensis* which show the decoupling of

tool production from the satisfaction of a concrete need, and a modularization of the use of tools. This modularization accelerates the accumulation of solution approaches and results in an increasing diversification in the material remains. (Tennie & Tomasello 2009; Haidle 2009; 2010).

- **Communal culture:** In communal culture self-consciousness (with awareness of other intentional actors) is extended to group consciousness: “I am acting in a group with others” can be shifted to “we as a group are acting”. Objectives are additionally set on a communal basis, and communal tools—especially communication tools and tools fostering group identity—broaden the behavioral spectrum. Symbolic artifacts as ornaments or art objects, the principal function or secondary purpose of which is the transmission of information, are closely connected to communal culture. To unleash their full potential they require not only individual producers and users, but also a related group of receivers and decoders of the messages. The more complex and coded a message is, the more details about the code must be known to understand it. Well-informed circles begin to separate from groups of outsiders. Communal culture can partially be equated with the concept of cultural modernity used in Paleolithic archaeology. Example: *Homo sapiens* today. (Conard 2010; Nowell 2010; Shennan 2001; Vanhaeren & d’Errico 2006; Wadley 2001).

The model for the extension of cultural capacity introduced above focuses on the transmission of information, on the amount and form of information transmitted, on the different processes of transmission, and the set of problems that can be approached by socially transmitted information.

Cultural capacity and cultural performance

The model presented above gives only a coarse sketch of the expansion of cultural capacities and has to be completed by the concept of cultural performance. While the cultural capacity represents the potential range of cultural expressions defined by biological, historical and individual factors, cultural performances represent the actual set of cultural items expressed by an individual, a population, or a species (Fig. 3). The larger the capacity, the larger is the range of corresponding performances. The available cultural capacity is never completely exhausted, rather different parts of it are used. These cultural performances can be perceived partly in archaeological assemblages, as well as in the set of behaviors of a living group. The cultural capacity cannot be directly observed, but instead must be deduced from several quasi-contemporaneous and conspecific performances.

Fig. 3 Different cultural performances (grey, blue, green, red) within a cultural capacity

Cultural capacity is expanding in the course of human evolution. Single cultural performances, in contrast, can be simpler in an advanced state of cultural capacity than in an earlier state due to different sections of the cultural potential applied. Thus, cultural evolution cannot be perceived as a clearly progressive development. In sum, however, the possible variety of cultural performances is expanding with the cultural capacity. Table 1 gives an overview of some requirements and some possible expressions of the different steps of cultural capacity introduced above.

Cultural capacity	When?	Who?	Requirements			Performance				Artistic representation			
			Cognitive requirements	Brain structure	Life history	Social structure	Climate zones	Ecological barriers of hominins	Material culture		Language	Subsistence	Fire
Communal culture	100 ka	H. sapiens?	Individual consciousness Planning depth extended to communal objectives Group consciousness			High pop. density, close distinct groups	Also arctic, arid	No barriers	Also communication tools, complementarity, trade, innovation rate low to high		technology?	Individual property Group property, territorialism	Group specific symbolic system Symbols artification on group level (dance, music, ornaments, burials etc.)
Cumulative culture	>300 ka	H. heidelbergensis?	process oriented learning, e.g. imitation, teaching, language?, planning depth extended to abstract individual objectives			composite cooperation	Also cold temperate	Extreme ranges of climate, extremely limited fresh water access	Also modular tools, composite tools, innovation rate low to medium		production transport	Long-term individual and group possession	Early aesthetics, artification on individual level
Delayed culture	3 Ma	hominins	Problem-solution-distance extended to effective chain, planning depth extended to sub-acute, but concrete individual objectives				Also mediterranean, warm temperate	Sea straits, high mountains, large rivers, limited fresh water access, extended ranges of climate	Also secondary tools, innovation rate low		maintenance use		
Basic culture		Chimpanzees, orangutans, australopithecines etc.	Self consciousness, planning depth attached to immediate and concrete individual objectives		extended childhood		Tropics and subtropics		number of traditions differing between geographical groups, only primary tools, innovation rate low				
Tradition		Crows, rats, etc.	result oriented learning, e.g. emulation						behavioral pattern, socially transmitted, as permanent character, only primary tools, innovation rate very low			Short-term individual possession	
Socially transmitted information		Bees, wolves, etc.				Social groups			{instant information, not materially fixed}				

Table 1. Steps of cultural capacity with requirements and possible expressions (preliminary version April 2011)

The nature of culture

The symposium “The nature of culture” seeks to follow the model of extension of cultural capacity from socially transmitted information to cultural identity. A fundamental question is whether all of the steps introduced in the model above are necessary, or even sufficient. While culture is widely accepted to occur in some animal species, cumulative culture is generally ascribed solely to the genus *Homo*. But what sort of cultural capacity is needed to produce Lower Paleolithic tools? Do they represent more than basic culture? Which characters would they need to be accepted as evidence of cumulative culture? Or, as another possibility, can or must cumulative culture be equated with the archaeological concept of cultural modernity, defined by a set of capacities and associated artifacts said to represent the basis of modern human behavior in all of its known facets? What then is the relation between communal cultural and cultural modernity? Yet more general questions arise. To what extent do the identified cultural stages allow behavioral plasticity and flexibility? Are changes in cultural competence bound to changes in life history (e.g. O’Connell et al. 1999; Nowell & White 2010)? Is there another source of evidence beside archaeologically recorded tools? And finally, how strongly is culture bound to ecology (Bird & O’Connell 2006)? Put even more simply, how cultural can culture be?

References

- Bird, D. W. & J. F. O’Connell 2006. Behavioral ecology and archaeology. *Journal of Archaeological Research* 14/2, 143-188.
- Byrne, R. W., P. J. Barnard, I. Davidson, V. M. Janik, W. C. McGrew, A. Miklósi & P. Wiessner 2004. Understanding culture across species. *TRENDS in Cognitive Sciences* 8/8, 341-346.
- Conard, N. J. 2010. Cultural modernity: consensus or conundrum? *PNAS* 107, 7621-7622.
- Davidson, I. & W. C. McGrew 2005. Stone tools and the uniqueness of human culture. *Journal of the Royal Anthropological Institute (N.S.)* 11, 793-817.
- Delagnes, A. & H. Roche 2005. Late Pliocene hominid knapping skills: The case of Lokalalei 2C, West Turkana, Kenya. *Journal of Human Evolution* 48, 435-472.
- Galef, B. G. Jr. 2004. Approaches to the study of traditional behaviors of free-living animals. *Learning & Behavior* 32/1, 53–61.

- Goren-Inbar, N. 2011. Culture and cognition in the Acheulian industry: a case study from Gesher Benot Ya'aqov. *Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society B* 366, 1038–1049.
- Haidle, M. N. 2008a. Kognitive und Kulturelle Evolution. *Erwägen – Wissen – Ethik* 19/2, 149-209.
- Haidle, M. N. 2008b. Verschiedene Welten. Umweltwahrnehmung und Umweltgestaltung im Laufe der menschlichen Evolution. In Knopf, Thomas (ed.), *Umweltverhalten in Geschichte und Gegenwart. Vergleichende Ansätze*. Attempto, Tübingen, 30-41.
- Haidle, M. N. 2010. Working memory capacity and the evolution of modern cognitive capacities - implications from animal and early human tool use. *Current Anthropology* 51/S1, Working memory: beyond language and symbolism, *Wenner-Gren Symposium Supplement* 1, S149-S166.
- Haidle, M. N. 2009. How to think a simple spear? In de Beaune, Sophie A., Frederick L. Coolidge & Thomas Wynn (eds.), *Cognitive archaeology and human evolution*. New York: Cambridge University Press, 57-73.
- Hammel, L. 2007. Der Kulturbegriff im wissenschaftlichen Diskurs und seine Bedeutung für die Musikpädagogik. Versuch eines Literaturberichts. *Zeitschrift für Kritische Musikpädagogik* 2007, 1-21.
- Henrich, J. & R. McElreath 2003. The evolution of cultural evolution. *Evolutionary Anthropology* 12, 123–135.
- Kroeber, A. L. & C. Kluckhohn 1952. *Culture: A critical review of concepts and definitions*. New York, Vintage books.
- McPherron, S. P., Z. Alemseged, C. W. Marean, J.G. Wynn, D. Reed, D. Geraads, R. Bobe & H. A. Béarat 2010. Evidence for stone-tool-assisted consumption of animal tissues before 3.39 million years ago at Dikika, Ethiopia. *Nature* 466, 857-860.
- Mesoudi, A., Whiten, A. & Laland, K. N. 2006. Towards a unified science of cultural evolution. *Behavioral and Brain Sciences*, 29, 329-383.
- Nowell, A. 2010. Defining Behavioral Modernity in the Context of Neandertal and Anatomically Modern Human Populations. *Annual Review of Anthropology* 39, 437–52.
- Nowell, A. & M. White 2010. Growing up in the Middle Pleistocene: Life history Strategies and their relationship to Acheulian industries. In April Nowell and Iain Davidson (eds.), *Stone Tools and the Evolution of Human Cognition*, University Press of Colorado, pp. 67-82.
- Rendell, Luke and Hal Whitehead 2001. Culture in whales and dolphins. *Behavioral and Brain Sciences*

24, 309-382.

O'Connell, J.F., K. Hawkes & N. G. Blurton-Jones 1999. Grandmothering and the evolution of *Homo erectus*. *Journal of Human Evolution* 36, 461-85.

Roche, H., A. Delagnes, J.-P. Brugal, C. Feibel, M. Kibunjia, V. Mourrek & P.-J. Texier 1999. Early hominid stone tool production and technical skill 2.34Myr ago in West Turkana, Kenya. *Nature* 399, 57-60.

Sharon, G., N. Alperson-Afil, N. Goren-Inbar 2011. Cultural conservatism and variability in the Acheulian sequence of Gesher Benot Ya'aqov. *Journal of Human Evolution* 60, 387-397.

Shennan, S. 2001. Demography and cultural Innovation: a model and its implications for the emergence of modern human culture. *Cambridge Archaeological Journal* 11/1, 5-16.

Tennie, C., J. Call & M. Tomasello 2009. Ratcheting up the ratchet: on the evolution of cumulative culture. *Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society B* 364, 2405-2415.

van Schaik, C. P., M. Ancrenaz, G. Borgen, B. Galdikas, C. D. Knott, I. Singleton, A. Suzuki, S. S. Utami & M. Merrill 2003. Orangutan cultures and the evolution of material culture. *Science* 299, 102-105.

Vanhaeren, M. & F. d'Errico 2006. Aurignacian ethno-linguistic geography of Europe revealed by personal ornaments. *Journal of Archaeological Science* 33, 1105-1128.

Wadley, L. 2001. What is cultural modernity? A general view and a South African perspective from Rose Cottage Cave. *Cambridge Archaeological Journal* 11/2, 201-21.

Whiten, A. 2009. The identification of culture in chimpanzees and other animals: From natural history to diffusion experiments. In K. N. Laland & B. G. Galef (Eds.) *The Question of Animal Culture*. pp 99-124. Cambridge, MA: Harvard University Press.

Whiten, A., J. Goodall, W. C. McGrew, T. Nishida, V. Reynolds, Y. Sugiyama, C. E. G. Tutin, R. W. Wrangham & C. Boesch 1999. Cultures in chimpanzees. *Nature* 399, 682-685.

Whiten, A., R. A. Hinde, K. N. Laland & C. B. Stringer 2010. Introduction: Culture evolves. *Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society B* 366, 938-948.

Whiten, A., K. Schick & N. Toth 2009. The evolution and cultural transmission of percussive technology: integrating evidence from paleoanthropology and primatology. *Journal of Human Evolution* 57, 420-435.

The Critical Pre-hominin Foundations of Hominin Cultural Evolution

Andrew Whiten

Centre for Social Learning and Cognitive Evolution, University of St Andrews, St. Andrews

The expansion of cultural capacity and material achievement that occurred in the course of hominin evolution, the central focus in this symposium, is principally documented within the stone age, which occupied the latter half of the period since the common ancestor of humans and chimpanzees lived (Whiten et al. 2011). Here I focus on reconstructing the evolution of the essential cultural foundations that made the hominin cultural expansion possible. This analysis logically takes the common human-chimpanzee ancestor as its principal focus, but can be extended much further back in time, as well as forwards to the beginnings of the stone age, insofar as there is little to document significant change from great ape levels of culture until then.

Taking the chimpanzee of today as a model of our common ancestor would invite several potential pitfalls (Whiten et al. 2010). Instead I analyse the cultural commonalities between ourselves and chimpanzees (and where possible, other apes) to draw inferences about the likely nature and scope of culture in our common ancestor. In recent papers I have suggested that where the goal is to compare cultural phenomena between humans, chimpanzees and other species, it is helpful to assign such phenomena to one of three major categories, each further subdivided into several subcategories (Whiten 2005, 2011).

The first category concerns the distribution of traditions in space and/or time. Here, commonalities between chimpanzees and humans suggest a common ancestry marked by the existence of regionally different, socially transmitted cultures each defined by multiple traditions spanning a variety of types of behaviour, including food processing techniques and tool repertoires, as well as social and sexual customs. Compared to hominins' later evolving cultural richness these would have been limited to only a handful of traditions and shown little sign of cumulative cultural change, if any.

The second category concerns the behavioural and material contents of culture. Of major interest from the perspective of the present symposium, chimpanzees share with ourselves a substantial suite of material traditions that incorporate large numbers of tool types and uses, including a range of percussive techniques that suggest important ancestral foundations for the innovations and cultural achievements of the stone age (Whiten, Schick and Toth 2009). I shall describe key features of this cultural content in more detail.

The third category concerns the psychological and behavioural processes and mechanisms underlying cultural transmission. Characteristics shared between chimpanzees and humans suggest a common ancestor would have possessed a suite of different social learning processes ranging from imitation to emulation (emulation is learning from the results of actions, rather than copying actions themselves). These processes would not have permitted the high fidelity copying characteristic of our own species today, nor would they have involved more than minimal forms of teaching, but from our experiments with apes we can infer that they would have been sufficient to sustain traditions including variations in, for example, percussive technologies. The extent of cultural capacity seen in great apes as a group, may explain their distinctive encephalisation (van Schaik and Burkart 2011).

The scenario outlined above for the cultural nature of our common ancestor corresponds to the level of multiple-tradition 'culture' in the broader evolutionary 'cultural pyramid' of Whiten and van Schaik (2007: see figure) on which Haidle, Conard and Bolus have elaborated to build their more comprehensive proposal for the evolution of culture. I shall suggest several respects in which both the original model and its more complex 'descendant' model, proposed by Haidle et al., might now be best refined.

The explanation for the expansion of cultural capacity and material capacity and material culture that characterised the stone age is suggested to lie in a unique interaction between the Africa Pliocene environmental change experienced by our ancestors, and the cultural potential already in existence, outlined in this paper.

References

- van Schaik, C. P. and Burkart, J. M. (2011). Social learning and evolution: the cultural intelligence hypothesis. *Phil. Trans. R. Soc. B* 366 997-1007.
- Whiten, A. (2005). The second inheritance system of chimpanzees and humans. *Nature*, 437, 52-55.
- Whiten, A. (2011). The scope of culture in chimpanzees, humans and ancestral apes. *Phil. Trans. R. Soc. B* 366 997-1007.
- Whiten, A., Hinde, R. A., Stringer, C. B. & Laland, K. N. (2011). Culture Evolves. *Phil. Trans. R. Soc. B* 366 938-948.
- Whiten, A., McGrew, W. C., Aiello, L. C. et al. (2010). Using extant species to model our past. *Science* 327, 410.
- Whiten, A. & van Schaik, C. P (2007). The evolution of animal 'cultures' and social intelligence. *Phil. Trans. R. Soc. B* 362, 603-620.
- Whiten, A., Schick, K. & Toth, N. (2009). The evolution and cultural transmission of percussive technology: integrating evidence from paleoanthropology and primatology. *J. Human Evolution* 57, 420-435.

For further publications see <https://risweb.st-andrews.ac.uk/portal>

See also www.cultureevolves.org for links and access to related documents

Stone Tools—Evidence of Something in Between Culture and Cumulative Culture

Iain Davidson

University of New England and Flinders University, Adelaide City

Thinking about the special role of culture in the evolutionary emergence of humans requires both a definition of what culture is and an understanding of how that definition is consistent with understandings of evolution. In this presentation, I will offer a definition of culture and show how it contributes to variation in the behaviour of humans and our ancestors. In doing so, I will endeavour to show how cultural behaviour among human ancestors may have differed from that of other members of the common ancestor. I will then show how it fits into an understanding of evolution as something that derives from natural selection operating on variation.

I will then consider how the characteristics associated with stone tools made a fundamental difference to the emergence of culture that is distinctively human. I will situate these observations in the context of the “model for the extension of cultural capacity” outlined for the symposium.

This paper will conclude with some consideration of the selective contexts for innovation in stone tool manufacture, including broader aspects of society and cognition, and the behavioural evidence from which we can make inferences about them in the archaeological record.

The Nature of the Earliest Hominin Cultures

Anne Delagnes

CNRS – PACEA/université Bordeaux 1, Talence

The first hominin cultures emerge between 2.6 and 2.3 Ma in several areas dispersed along the northern extension of the East African Rift System, over a distance of about 1000 km, from the Afar triangle in the north to the Turkana basin in the south. No more than four site complexes yield archaeological sites that are correlated with this time period: Gona, Hadar, Omo (Ethiopia) and Lokalalei (Kenya) site complexes. They form the earliest indisputable evidence of hominin culture. They all occur within geological and fossil-bearing formations that cover a much longer time range and start respectively from 4.5 Ma (Nachukui formation: Lokalalei site complex), 3.6 Ma (Shungura Formation: Omo site complex), 3.4 Ma (Hadar Formation: Hadar site complex) and 2.94 Ma (Budisima Formation: Gona site complex) (Woldegabriel et al. 2000). A number of hominin taxa: robust or gracile australopithecines, as well as Early Homo, could be the authors of this first hominin culture. The only plausible evidence of direct association between hominin fossils and archaeological occurrences comes from the Hadar Formation, where a maxilla of an early Homo (AL 666) has been found in close spatial and stratigraphic correlation with stone tools in a horizon dated to circa 2.33 Ma (Kimbel et al. 1996).

One of the key questions that emerge from these cultural remains is whether they reflect the first stage of stone tool production or whether they relate to an already advanced stage of tool-making. They also raise the questions of a rapid *versus* gradual development of hominin cultural capacity and of a monocentric *versus* polycentric emergence. At 2.6 Ma, the oldest stone tool assemblages, found at Gona (OGS 6a and OGS 7) (Semaw 2000; Semaw et al. 1997), do not reflect a novice lithic production. All the basic physical and gestural principles of hard rock fragmentation are acquired at this stage. The same holds true for most of the sites comprised between 2.6 and 2.3 Ma, with some discrepancies from one site to another. These discrepancies certainly reflect unequal technical skills, but more acute technological and chronological data are still required to assess whether they may correspond to distinct stages of apprenticeship.

Considering the intensive surveys that are carried out in these formations from several decades, it is unlikely that the absence of archaeological evidence prior to 2.6 Ma may be a result of an archaeological bias. Moreover, even if the technological patterns that characterize the first stone tools were the result of elementary, unpatterned or unskilled behaviors, it should be possible to distinguish them from natural implements, as has been done for the low-elaborated Lokalalei 1 assemblage. The petrographic composition of the assemblages compared with the composition of the natural outcrops accessible during site occupation, seems a relevant criteria, in addition to technological criteria, for recognizing a hominid-made assemblage. With few exceptions (eg. Hadar A.L. 894) (Goldman-Neuman and Hovers 2009), raw material selectivity is indeed a pattern that characterizes the earliest known lithic series.

At a macro-regional scale, sites are distributed in two core areas some one thousand kilometers apart: the Afar Rift (Gona, Hadar) and the Omo Basin (Lokalalei, Omo). The scarce available data concerning early hominin mobility patterns suggest that they exploited small subsistence territories. If we accept such assumption, connections between the two core areas seem very unlikely, whereas displacements of groups between Gona and Hadar sites on one hand, Lokalalei and Omo sites on the other hand, look more plausible. The picture that emerges from such paleogeographic settings would support the assumption of at least two homes of emergence for the earliest hominin cultures.

At a micro-regional scale, Lokalalei site complex gives relevant indications on the cognitive abilities involved during the first stages of toolmaking and their variation in time. The oldest occurrence, found at Lokalalei 1, documents low elaborated flaking sequences (Kibunjia 1994) which contrast significantly with the organized flaking process evidenced at the younger Lokalalei 2c site (Delagnes and Roche 2005). The differences are mainly visible in terms of nodule selectivity, planning depth, blow precision, frequency of flaking accidents, productivity and regularity of gestures. They clearly indicate an important cognitive difference between the two groups of knappers. Moreover, the technical skills documented at Lokalalei 2c imply a social transmission that rests on the replication of gestural sequences and not merely on single gestures.

Despite some marked cognitive differences, stone tool production prior to 2 Ma is characterized by a set of constant technical features which rest on the prevalence of flaking sequences intended for the obtention of small sharp-edged flakes which look perfectly adapted for cutting soft tissues. Pounding, shaped, and retouched implements are very rare, which points for a still limited array of functional needs. Raw material procurement prioritizes in most instances fine-grained lavas (eg. Gona, Lokalalei) (Harmand 2009; Stout et al. 2005), supporting the assumption of implements intended primarily for cutting tasks. These technical features are still present in the Oldowan assemblages dated after 2 Ma, in association with a diversity of end-products that did not exist before. Such shifts raise a number of issues related to the homogeneity of the Oldowan, the driven factors (eg. environmental or biological) and the nature of the changes (eg. cultural, functional, cognitive) that occur during the earliest stages of stone tool production, between 2.6 and 1.8 Ma.

References

- Delagnes, A., and H. Roche. 2005. "Late Pliocene hominid knapping skills : The case of Lokalalei 2C, West Turkana, Kenya." *Journal of Human Evolution* 48:435-72.
- Goldman-Neuman, T., and E. Hovers. 2009. "Methodological Considerations in the Study of Oldowan Raw Material Selectivity: Insights from A.L. 894 (Hadar, Ethiopia)." Pp. 71-84 in *Interdisciplinary Approaches to the Oldowan*, edited by E. Hovers and D.R. Braun. Dordrecht: Springer Science+ Business Media B.V.
- Harmand, S. 2009. "Variability in raw material selectivity at the late Pliocene sites of Lokalalei, West Turkana, Kenya." Pp. 85-97 in *Interdisciplinary Approaches to the Oldowan*, edited by E. Hovers and D.R. Braun. Dordrecht: Springer.
- Kibunjia, M. 1994. "Pliocene archaeological occurrences in the Lake Turkana basin." *Journal of Human Evolution* 27:159-71.
- Kimbel, W.H., R.C. Walter, D.C. Johanson, K.E. Reed, J.L. Aronson, Z. Assefa, C.W. Marean, G.G. Eck, R. Bobe, E. Hovers, Y. Rak, C. Vondra, T. Yemane, D. York, Y. Chen, N.M. Evensen, and P.E. Smith. 1996. "Late Pliocene *Homo* and Oldowan Tools from the Hadar Formation (Kada Hadar Member), Ethiopia." *Journal of Human Evolution* 31:549-67.
- Semaw, S. 2000. "The world's oldest stone artefacts from Gona, Ethiopia : their implications for understanding stone technology and patterns of human evolution between 2.6-1.5 million year ago." *Journal of Archaeological Science* 27:1197-214.
- Semaw, S., P. Renne, J.W.K. Harris, C.S. Feibel, R.L. Bernor, N. Fesseha, and K. Mowbray. 1997. "2.5-million-year-old stone tools from Gona, Ethiopia." *Nature* 385:333-36.
- Stout, D., J. Quade, S. Semaw, M.J. Rogers, and N.E. Levin. 2005. "Raw material selectivity of the earliest stone toolmakers at Gona, Afar, Ethiopia." *Journal of Human Evolution* 48:365-80.
- Woldegabriel, G., G. Heiken, T.D. White, B. Asfaw, W.K. Hart, and P.R. Renne. 2000. "Volcanism, tectonism, sedimentation, and the paleoanthropological record in the Ethiopian Rift System." Pp. 83-99 in *Volcanic Hazards and Disasters in Human Antiquity*, edited by F.W. McCoy and G. Heiken. Boulder, Colorado: Geological Society of America.

Notes for discussion: Is it possible to differentiate between basic culture and delayed culture?

Cumulative Culture - Cognitive and Social Prerequisites and Possible Material Outcomes

Claudio Tennie, David Braun and Shannon P. McPherron

Dept. of Developmental and Comparative Psychology
Max Planck Institute for Evolutionary Anthropology, Leipzig

Recently the expansion of the investigation of tool use and behavioral patterns in chimpanzees and other non-human animals has changed our view of our closest living relatives. Rather than culture separating us from the apes, it appears as if culture may be a unifying dimension of the higher primate lineage. However, despite the apparent similarities between human cultures and similar-looking patterns of behavior in chimpanzees and other ape species, there do appear to be differences that make human culture unique. Specifically, the nature of human cultural change is associated with a ratcheting effect usually referred to as cumulative cultural evolution and may be a unique feature of the hominin lineage. Tomasello has suggested that one important underlying learning mechanism of cumulative culture is imitation. While it is currently debated whether learning through imitation is present in the non-human primates, Tennie has offered an alternative learning model for chimpanzees called the zone of latent solutions (ZLS). The ZLS model is based on the premise that all documented chimpanzee behaviors can be learned by a naïve individual without access to or knowledge of prior learned behaviors and that behaviors spread within a group through social learning via low-fidelity copying. The question we ask here is whether the ZLS model can explain the behaviors documented in the earliest archaeological record without recourse to cumulative culture. If so, the question then becomes when did cumulative culture first appear. First, we argue that the Oldowan, with its simple core and flake technology, very likely falls within the ZLS model. Second we consider whether the Acheulian, characterized by the handaxe, might also fall within this model. We conclude with some considerations of how we might better refine our archaeological tests to better understand the origins of cumulative culture in the hominin lineage.

Scarce but Significant: The Limestone Component of the Acheulian of Gesher Benot Ya'aqov, Israel

Nira Alperson-Afil and Naama Goren-Inbar

Institute of Archaeology, Hebrew University of Jerusalem, Mt. Scopus, 91905, Jerusalem

A variety of scientific fields are involved in the attempt to explore hominin cultural complexity, including evolutionary biology, brain research, animal behavior, and ethnography. And yet, the only *direct* evidence for the behavior and technological skills of our ancestors is available through the archaeological record. Analyses of their material culture remains can contribute substance and illustrate cultural complexity. Lithic *chaînes opératoires* are expressed in the search, selection, and procurement of raw materials, followed by the production, modification, use, and discard of the artifacts. The different stages of the reduction sequence attest to various cognitive abilities as well as cultural complexity in human Paleolithic history. These involve foresight and planning, technological skills, fitting typo-technological images to particular materials, problem solving and flexibility, all associated with a vast knowledge of the environmental resources and the ways by which they can beexploited and fit into the work plan.

Located in the African Great Rift, the site of Gesher Benot Ya'aqov (GBY) is bedded in the Benot Ya'akov Formation. Excavations have revealed that this formation was deposited by the paleo-Lake Hula during the Early–Middle Pleistocene. The depositional sequence includes extensive lake and lake-margin environments in which evidence of human activities is provided by a series of 14 archaeological horizons rich in paleontological, paleobotanical, and archaeological assemblages, assigned to MIS 18.

Since the beginning of excavations at Gesher Benot Ya'aqov, the remains of its Acheulian material culture have been continuously studied. The analyses have demonstrated affinities with the African tradition and revealed various technological and behavioral traits of the ancient hominins. Recently, an in-depth investigation of the GBY limestone component has been carried out, resulting in illumination of the role of this component in Levantine Acheulian assemblages. Our study reveals that the limestone component, procured from fluvial deposits in the vicinity of the site, was transported to

the lake margin and was exploited throughout the occupational sequence. Limestone nodules were brought to the site for a particular function that necessitated a specific size range and morphology. While size selection is easily recognized through metrical analyses, function is more elusive and is studied through techno-morpho-typological classification.

The limestone component at GBY includes a small sample of flakes and flake tools in addition to three categories of cores/core tools: percussors, chopping tools, and cores. Analyses of the three main categories of cores/core-tools illustrate that they exhibit a gradual reduction in several morpho-technological attributes, suggesting that the GBY limestone artifacts originate primarily in a single reduction process.

The limestone reduction sequence begins with targeting the most suitable nodules for use as percussors. The operation of these percussors sometimes caused breakage of the artifacts and hence accidentally produced flakes typical of working accidents. When percussors were broken, a sharp working edge was often formed, and a second morphotype, chopping tools, was created. A third morphotype represents different types of cores. We view these three morphotypes as inter-related consecutive options. The analyses show that once a morphotype was inadequate for use it was transformed into another one, a reduction sequence characterized by the reduction of dimensions

from one type to the other. The primary motive of the GBY hominins in obtaining limestone nodules was their use as percussors. Thus, the other limestone artifacts can be considered byproducts.

The fact that these byproducts appear in the reduction sequence in a formal, consistent manner is evidence of contingency. The ability to transform one type into another while diverging from the original plan implies cultural complexity as well as flexibility. As with other aspects of the lithic assemblages of GBY, the limestone component exhibits consistent homogeneity along the time trajectory for thousands of years. This conservatism of the transmission of knowledge about specific raw materials, their reduction sequences, and the flexible variations within them is typical of a "complex" culture.

Is Increasing Technological, Behavioural and Cognitive Flexibility an Effect of Cumulative Culture?

Stone Age Hunting Weapons as Proxy for the Evolution of Human Flexibility

Marlize Lombard

Department of Anthropology and Development Studies

University of Johannesburg, Johannesburg

In this paper I ask a series of questions relating to technological, behavioural and cognitive flexibility and how these concepts relate to the idea of cumulative culture as represented in the Stone Age archaeological record. It is an exploratory paper, mainly based on my long-term interest in the evolution of hunting technology, and recent collaborative work with Miriam Haidle on the potential cognitive implications of the production and use of bow-and-arrow technology during the Middle Stone Age in southern Africa. I introduce three basic types of hunting technologies for which we have archaeological evidence from > 300 ka to ~ 60 ka.

The only traces of early human culture are reflected in archaeological remains that most often represent technology. By studying and hypothesising about technologies in different ways we may be able to gain some insight into the more abstract notions of behavioural and cognitive flexibility. For example, drawing from a range of methods we can consider:

- a) With what tools were made – assess levels of flexibility during the collection and preparation of materials.
- b) How tools were made – assess levels of flexibility during tool production.
- c) Why tools were made (function) – assess levels of flexibility regarding the application of technology.

For example, when we explore what the Schöningen spears were made of, and how they were produced, we find a surprisingly intricate answer. Miriam Haidle's work shows us that what seems like a simple, single-substance object made by *Homo heidelbergensis* more than 300 ka ago requires the collection and preparation of several other materials before production can begin. If we accept that sharp-edged stone tools were used to remove bark and smooth and sharpen the wood, and that heat was used to shape and/or harden the spears, then the spears already represent a decoupling of satisfaction and basic need (where small operational units, each with its own intermediate aims, can be put together in a modular, flexible way in different operational sequences), a cognitive and cultural trait seemingly unique to *Homo*.

Such objects need not only be used as hand-delivered hunting weapons, they would function equally well as digging sticks, armatures for defence, walking sticks and stakes that can be driven into the ground for various purposes. Thus, the notion of modifying a wooden stick, into a long, straight, strong, sharpened object (such as a spear from Schöningen), can exponentially increase the range of behaviours with which an individual interacts with her/his conditions and situations. As a result, individuals equipped with wooden spears are much more prepared for, and flexible within, their environments than without – whether these environments are physical, economical or social.

The addition of several independent elements forming a single, composite tool with enhanced properties, such as a stone-tipped spear or knife, represents the concept of modular combination or the further cognitive element of 'composition'. We will probably never know how, or how many times, the idea of a hafted tool was 'invented' over the past 300 ka, but it is an innovation that radically changed the world of hominin technology. Composition offers increased flexibility in different contexts, a range of solutions can be applied to a single problem, or diverse needs can be met with one solution. Fitness options regarding hunting, meat processing, foraging and defence are increased exponentially for individuals equipped with stone-tipped spears and knives, as opposed to those with simple wooden spears and a handful of loose stone flakes. Evidence for stone-tipped spears (or other composite/hafted implements) in the archaeological record, therefore, represents a powerful increase in technological, behavioural and cognitive flexibility compared to that of simple wooden spears and/or hand-held stone tools. Notwithstanding its complexity, it is a cognitive trait shared by *Homo sapiens* with several other *Homo* species, including *Homo neanderthalensis* and *Homo heidelbergensis* in Eurasia, and archaic modern *Homo* in Africa.

The invention of the bow and arrow used to be closely linked to the late Upper Palaeolithic in Europe, and thought to be a recent invention in Eurasia and the Americas. Recent evidence, however, indicates that this technology was in use during the Middle Stone Age in sub-Saharan Africa by ~ 64 ka. Whereas more steps may be involved in bow-and-arrow production than in stone-tipped spear production, broken down into its individual operational units, the production of a bow or an arrow is probably no more complex than the production of any other composite tool. On the other hand, as soon a bow-and-arrow is used together, as complementary tool set, it represents the cognitive concept of technological symbiosis – i.e., the ability to conceptualize a set of independent, yet inter-dependent tools. With technological symbiosis, the advantages of modularization increase exponentially into what can be referred to as advanced modularization. Consequently, flexibility regarding decision-making and taking action is amplified. It allows a range of cognitive and behavioral complexity and flexibility that is basic to human behavior today.

Do these hunting technologies reflect cumulative culture? In our briefing document, cumulative culture is defined as changes that are built upon one another and accumulate over time. The suggested outcome is that the same problems need not be solved repeatedly. Rather, already available solutions or options can be adapted or further developed. The process is compared to a ratchet – a wheel or bar with teeth along the edge and metal piece that fits between the teeth, allowing movement in one direction only.

At first glance, the answer to the question posed above has to be ‘yes’. Using the three weapon systems introduced here, and their rough chronological appearance in the Stone Age archaeological record, we can construct the following hypothetical ratchet:

1. Ability to use and alter objects – basic technology;
2. Ability to change objects with other objects before use – modularization;
3. Ability to combine objects into single units – composition;
4. Ability to produce and use complementary tool sets – technological symbiosis/advanced modularization.

Yet, considering our archaeological and historical records in more detail, I’m not convinced that a ratchet or the ratchet effect is the most appropriate illustration of what is reflected in the cultural remains associated with humans. As illustrated above, the analogy can be used as a course-grained reconstruction of long-term technological/cultural evolution, but it fails to explain or help understand episodes of simplification often encountered in our archaeological and historical records. A ratchet, allowing movement in a single direction only, is perhaps too inflexible and too close to

previous unilinear perceptions of cultural evolution to explain the irregular cultural record associated with human behaviour. The archaeological and historical records do not always show a continuous accretion of innovations as expected when cumulative culture is compared with a ratchet. Rather, when we afford it a closer look, it seems as though complex technologies may have been invented, discarded and re-invented or re-introduced over time and space – most probably as a result of a variety of environmental, demographic and social factors. Whereas the ratchet effect may be used effectively to illustrate the latent capacity for certain types of behaviours, I wonder if a model of humans negotiating a rugged fitness landscape (historical context, demography and environment), supplied with mountaineering gear (technology/culture), is perhaps not more appropriate to illustrate the evolution of human cognitive and behavioural flexibility.

The Evolution of Play and Its Role in the Extension of Cultural Competence

April Nowell

Department of Anthropology, University of Victoria, Victoria

One of the questions that arises out of this workshop is whether changes in life history correspond to changes in cultural capacity. In other words, as our hominin ancestors transitioned from one life history strategy to another can we document concomitant shifts in the extension of cultural capacity? This is not a simple question. Life history, often referred to as reproductive turnover or the 'speed of life', is "the allocation of an organism's energy for growth, maintenance and reproduction . . . it is fundamentally a life strategy adopted by an organism to maximize fitness in a world of limited energy (Dean and Smith 2009:119)." As such life history is not just one 'thing'; it is the sum total of life history-related variables such as gestation length, age at weaning, age at first and last reproduction and longevity that can tell us about the rate and timing of important life history events. Life-history strategies are fluid and where we recognize breaks is somewhat arbitrary. The same can be said for cultural capacity. Thus, the short answer to this question could be both yes or no depending on which variable or suite of variables is studied; how much change is 'enough change' to be considered something different and whether we ask this question at the level of the individual or the population.

Workshop organizers have argued that the extension of cultural capacity can be thought of in terms of the amount, form and processes of the transmission of information. In this paper I will look at the evidence for the evolution and extension of the uniquely hominin life history stages of childhood and adolescence and I will consider the relationship between these stages, the evolution of play, the transmission of information through peer to peer interaction, and the extension of cultural capacity. I will conclude by outlining the implications of these relationships for our understanding and interpretation of the archaeological record.

The Relationship Between Technological, Cognitive and Cultural Complexity

Lyn Wadley

School of Geography, Archaeology and Environmental Studies and The Institute for Human Evolution, University of the Witwatersrand, Johannesburg

The definition of human culture is difficult to separate from that of animal culture, except that a number of cultural attributes can be simultaneously attributed to humans and not to animals. This is not an issue that arises when trying to define what is meant by culture in the modern world or even in the world that was occupied by people who were physically like us at 100,000 years ago. As archaeologists, we cannot access culture or cognition directly; we can only interpret the level of cultural or cognitive complexity from circumstantial evidence. We also do not excavate technology; we infer a level of technology from artefacts and the contexts from which they were recovered. Interpreting technological, cognitive and cultural complexity requires carefully constructed bridging theory between archaeologically-recovered data and interpretations about behaviour and human capacity. Some technological strategies that we infer from the Middle Stone Age record in Africa seem to have the potential to inform us about the cognitive abilities achieved by people in the past. Amongst these is trapping and snaring. The humble and technically simple snare implies complex executive functions of the brain enabling people to hold in mind a strategy and action that is out-of-sight. A great many new social circumstances are enabled through the invention of the snare. Thus complex technology is not a prerequisite for cognitive or cultural complexity, though it may also inform us of these states. The creation of compound adhesives in the Middle Stone Age is one way in which multi-faceted technology requiring multi-tasking and even abstract thought can provide a clue to complex cognition possessed by artisans in the past.

Notes for discussion: How can cumulative culture be traced in the archaeological record?

Demography and Cultural Identity

Stephen Shennan

Institute of Archaeology, UCL, London

The role of culture – by which I mean ‘information capable of affecting individuals’ behaviour which they acquire from other members of their species through teaching, imitation and other forms of social transmission’ (Richerson and Boyd 2005) – in human evolution remains unclear, and in general its importance has been assumed rather than demonstrated. Boyd and Richerson and others have generated a powerful theoretical framework and specific models that demonstrate the role it can have in improving human adaptiveness by providing a basis for making difficult decisions under uncertainty. Information which has led to successful decisions in the past becomes encoded and available to future generations, through a mechanism that can act more quickly than encoding information in genes. However, it is remarkable how little work has actually been done in testing hypotheses about the selective value of real cultural phenomena. The relative costs and benefits of different forms of lithics, for example, are still unclear. The debate about the origins of ‘behavioural modernity’ exemplifies a lot of the issues.

The understandable desire on the part of many is to have an index of the existence of genetically-evolved human capacities, hence the emphasis on art and religion; it is worth noting though that while we can potentially establish the novelty of these capacities in relation to our closest living relatives it is far less obviously that we can do the same with closer relations such as the Neanderthals. In any event, the problem is that behaviour is situation specific and thus the presence or absence of a particular behaviour, or certainly evidence of its presence in archaeological residues, cannot be taken as a reliable index.

For behavioural ecologists the situation-specificity is the only thing that matters. Thus time-consuming complex technologies will be adopted if the investment pays off and dropped if the circumstances that provide the basis for the payoffs change. From the perspective of what we might

call 'strong behavioural ecology', culture in the sense defined above, or in just about any other, is effectively irrelevant, though it is increasingly recognised there can be a feedback loop from what people did in the past to what they do in the present as a result of the process of 'niche construction', in which past actions change the environment for present ones.

The dual inheritance approach accepts the situation-specificity but proposes that what people do depends not just on the situation they find themselves in but on factors to do with the transmission of information in populations. From this perspective the disappearance of a complex technology could occur not because it no longer paid off but because some external factor such as a decrease in population size led to its loss, despite its continuing usefulness. Conversely, if successful innovations are relatively improbable, and not likely to be invented whenever they are required, they are more likely to appear in large populations because more opportunities will be generated.

There is now a variety of theoretical models that postulate links between population size and cultural complexity or adaptiveness. The paper will review these models and their implications including identity issues, and their relation to population density. It will also consider some case studies on later periods than the Palaeolithic that are relevant to the issues under discussion.

Cultural identity in Neanderthals?

Thorsten Uthmeier

Institut für Ur- und Frühgeschichte, Friedrich-Alexander-Universität, Erlangen-Nürnberg.

After defining cultural identity and the different social agents confined to it (e.g. individuals, intimate and extended families, local to regional groups/bands and collectives), the paper discusses Middle Paleolithic cultural elements that may be used to operationalize key attributes of cultural identity. Although it is agreed upon the fact that behavior in itself may also be part of cultural identity, e.g. patterns of site and land use, or hunting strategies, it is concluded that due to the long temporal span for a full comprehension, these might be more important for the inner group creation of identity rather than distinction between groups. In general, it is assumed that among man others, objects of all-day use, combined with the technology and method to produce them, may well function as such.

In a second step, a correlation between social agents and Middle Paleolithic classes of archaeological context (refitting, burial, industry) is proposed. However, first problems occur here: given the temporal depth in the spatial distribution of sites of one and the same industry, it is difficult to identify local and regional groups. Because demographic modeling as well as mtDNA analysis point to low population densities as well as totals, it cannot be excluded that on the long run territories of local groups are much larger than raw material transportation distances suggest.

The second part of the paper is dedicated to a case study. For the late Middle Paleolithic with bifacial tools (Mousterian of Acheulean tradition, Micoquian, Eastern Micoquian) it is shown that modes of blank production and reduction sequences (and, respectively, the material remains of them) are objects of cultural identity, and how divers these items are on large spatial scale within the same time window. By incorporating lifeways (land use patterns) and social organization of these groups/collectives, a context is reconstructed to again search for cultural identity on individual and group level.

Tracing Cultural Identity in Early Upper Paleolithic Stone and Organic Tools

Michael Bolus

ROCEEH, Heidelberg Academy of Sciences and Humanities, Tübingen

Discussions about identity in the Upper Paleolithic usually focus on art, decorated objects, personal ornaments, or, in more general terms, objects with symbolic contents (see, for instance, Bar-Yosef 2002; Vanhaeren and d'Errico 2006; Bolus and Conard 2008; Conard 2008), while organic tools and especially stone artifacts have been considered to a much lesser degree (e.g., Close 1978; Sackett 1982; Barton 1997). Basically, one can distinguish between group or social identity and personal identity, and most of the relevant papers are dealing with the former rather than with the latter.

Style seems to be a crucial topic when trying to trace identity in prehistoric times. While most colleagues seem to agree on this, the definition of style varies within the relevant key papers. Polly Wiessner (1983) in her study on Kalahari San projectile points distinguishes between assertive style which carries information about personal identity, separating the individual from similar group members, and emblematic style which is an active means of establishing group identity, while C. Michael Barton (1997) in his study on stone tools, style, and social identity uses the terms 'passive style' and 'active style'. Following Barton, both assertive style and emblematic style are representatives of active style. For him, individual social groups should be characterized by particular variants of a lithic artifact class. Still another approach is suggested by James R. Sackett (1982) who uses the term 'isochrestic style' which refers to choices made between variants that are equivalent in use.

With these definitions in mind, how can we trace style in stone and organic tools and determine its implications for recognizing cultural identity then?

Lyn Wadley (2003), viewing style as the repeated patterning that is geographically and chronologically restricted, argues that lithic assemblage variability can reflect active style, in the sense that stone tools can act as indices of social identity, but she emphasizes the tempo of technological change. We have to be aware, however, that variability in lithic assemblages not necessarily reflects style but may also be due to functional variability (see Bolus 2010).

Analogous to Wiessner analyzing (metal) San projectile points, many colleagues dealing with style in stone artifacts also concentrate on projectiles such as Solutrean leaf points or Paleoindian

points. For the European Aurignacian this approach is not very promising since projectile technology is based on points made of organic materials. It may be different for early Upper Paleolithic assemblages of Fumane type or for assemblages of the Ahmarian where lithic points are present. As Sackett (1982) points out, style may also be found in unmodified stone artifacts and strategies for core reduction, but systematic analyses are rare yet. An attempt has been made by Philip Nigst (2009) who interprets technological differences between assemblages from the MP-UP transition and the early Upper Paleolithic in the Middle Danube region as seemingly related to the cultural identity stored in technological styles and passed on between generations (Nigst 2009, 412). Another promising approach by Héloïse Koehler to infer identity from technological behaviors, based on the detailed analysis of Middle Paleolithic assemblages from the Paris Basin, should also be mentioned (Koehler 2009).

With regard to organic tools, some information is provided by special tool types such as slender pointed ivory objects, perhaps projectile points, found in the lowest Aurignacian layers from Hohle Fels and Geißenklösterle in the Swabian Jura (Bolus and Conard 2006). They differ strongly from the typical split-base points and seem to carry a fairly regional signature. As far as split-base points, themselves, are concerned, their dimensions as well as their shape vary from site to site so that it may be asked if these differences could be explained in terms of style or cultural identity.

Parameters which should be regarded in more detail in the future concern lithic raw-materials and their transport distances. Can the use of special raw-materials for the production of special tools indicate identity? Martina Barth (2007) in her study on Gravettian organic tools from the Swabian Jura could demonstrate that among the Swabian sites there are differences in the raw materials used for the production of special tool types and that this picture in turn differs from the ones observed in Western Europe and in eastern Central Europe. It will be a future task to find out if similar tendencies are visible with regard to the Aurignacian assemblages.

Given these differences observed in various regions, one may ask to what extent differences between more or less contemporary technocomplexes such as early Aurignacian, Fumanian, and Ahmarian may be indicators of different cultural identities. In addition to this more synchronous view regarding larger parts of Europe and the Near East, a diachronous view for sites within a clear-defined region such as the Swabian Jura, the Périgord, or northern Italy will be promising.

This paper will present questions rather than answers. It is meant to arouse discussion and to direct the focus on stone and organic tools which are often neglected when discussing style and identity in the Paleolithic. In any case it seems obvious that stone and organic tools alone will certainly not be sufficient to trace style and cultural identity in early Upper Paleolithic assemblages. We will surely need data added by other artifact categories such as personal ornaments, decorated

objects and art objects. Only from a combination of all these data, we will learn more about group organization, social differences, and, finally, identity in the early Upper Paleolithic. Nevertheless, once the necessary systematic analyses are available, stone and organic tools will also hopefully help us to better understand the step from cumulative culture to communal culture.

References

- Barth, M. 2007: Familienbande? Die gravettienzeitlichen Knochen- und Geweihgeräte des Aichtals (Schwäbische Alb). *Tübinger Arbeiten zur Urgeschichte* 4. Rahden/Westf.: Verlag Marie Leidorf.
- Barton, C. M. 1997: Stone Tools, Style, and Social Identity: an Evolutionary Perspective on the Archaeological Record. *Archaeological Papers of the American Anthropological Association* 7, 141-156.
- Bar-Yosef, O. 2002: The Upper Paleolithic Revolution. *Annual Review of Anthropology* 31, 363-391.
- Bolus, M. 2010: Continuity or Hiatus? The Swabian Aurignacian and the Transition to the Gravettian. In: C. Neugebauer Maresch and L. R. Owen (eds.), *New Aspects of the Central and Eastern European Upper Palaeolithic – methods, chronology, technology and subsistence*. Wien: Verlag der Österreichischen Akademie der Wissenschaften, 139-150.
- Bolus, M. and Conard, N. J. 2006: Zur Zeitstellung von Geschosspitzen aus organischen Materialien im späten Mittelpaläolithikum und Aurignacien. *Archäologisches Korrespondenzblatt* 36, 1-15.
- Bolus, M. and Conard, N. J. 2008: What can we say about the spatial-temporal distribution of early Aurignacian innovations? *Eurasian Prehistory* 5(2), 19-29.
- Close, A. E. 1978: The Identification of Style in Lithic Artefacts. *World Archaeology* 10, 223-237.
- Conard, N. J. 2008: A Critical View of the Evidence for a Southern African Origin of Behavioural Modernity. *South African Archaeological Society Goodwin Series* 10, 175-179
- Koehler, H. 2009: *Comportements et identité techniques au Paléolithique moyen (Weichsélien ancien) dans le Bassin parisien: une question d'échelle d'analyse?* Ph.D. thesis, University of Paris-Nanterre, published electronically.
- Nigst, P. R. 2009: The Early Upper Palaeolithic in the Middle Danube region: A regional study using the evidence of Willendorf II, Stratzing 94, Vedrovice V, and Stránská skála IIIc. Unpublished Ph.D. thesis, University of Leipzig.
- Sackett, J. R. 1982: Approaches to Style in Lithic Archaeology. *Journal of Anthropological Archaeology* 1, 59-112.
- Vanhaeren, M. and d'Errico, F. 2006: Aurignacian ethno-linguistic geography of Europe revealed by personal ornaments. *Journal of Archaeological Science* 33, 1105-1128.
- Wadley, L. 2003: How some archaeologists recognize culturally modern behavior. *South African Journal of Science* 99, 247-250.
- Wiessner, P. 1983: Style and Social Information in Kalahari San Projectile Points. *American Antiquity* 48, 253-276.

Notes for discussion: Communal culture vs. cultural modernity - a comparison of the material evidence of the two concepts regarding cultural capacity and cultural performances

Aurignacian Evidence—Culture Defining Identity, Culture Giving Identity

Marian Vanhaeren

CNRS UMR 7041 ArScAn, Ethnologie préhistorique, Paris

Today, personal ornaments are a peculiar and universal feature of human cultures and have come to play an important role in the debates on the emergence of modern cultures and the evolution of our ancestors' cognitive abilities. Most authors agree in categorizing beads as one of the hallmarks of modern cultures. Beads are interpreted as a behaviour in which standardised transferable items are displayed on the physical body to project symbolic meaning on the members of the same or neighbouring groups. For this reason personal ornaments are regarded as unambiguous symbolic material culture and their appearance in the archaeological record is seen as a sign that the associated human populations had symbolic communication systems. Divergent opinions exist, however, as to the dating of the first evidence of bead use, the taxonomic status of the first bead makers, the unique or multiple origin beads, the mechanism explaining their invention, and the factors responsible for their variation over time.

Until recently the invention of personal ornaments was considered as synonymous with the colonisation of Europe by Anatomically modern populations bearing the Aurignacian toolkit, some 40 ky ago. The discovery of personal ornaments at African and Near eastern sites older than 40 ky contradicts a European recent origin of bead making and use. However, it raises the question of whether, due to their apparent simple nature, these early instances reflect symbolic systems qualitatively comparable to those recorded in present day and historically known human societies or mirror different cognitive settings. The latter hypothesis may find support in the fact that no continuity or increasing complexity is observed at present between the first bead traditions and those developing after ca 40 kya in Europe, the former in the observation that archaeological and present day unquestionably modern societies with a limited number of bead types do exist, suggesting the use of few bead types does not necessarily make you less modern. In order to test these alternative scenarios we must gain a better insight in the way earliest beads were used and the degree of cognitive

and social complexity this use implied. In traditional societies they play at least fourteen different and often multiple roles (e.g. they may be used to beautify the body, function as 'love letters' in courtship, or as amulets, exchange media, expressions of individual and group identity, markers of age, class, gender, wealth or social status) which offer varied and rich information on the individuals, social groups, and societies that used them. The variety of functions that personal ornaments have in human societies may be reconstructed through application of specific methods.

Here we provide an overview of the available data and interpretations surrounding this category of the archaeological record and investigate if observed patterns of bead occurrences are correlated with factors such as cultural contact, environmental stress, population increase, cultural drift. We argue that it is important in an evolutionary perspective, to investigate the role(s) beadwork played in the course of time and that the earliest evidence for bead use from Europe, Eurasia, the Near East, Australia and Africa suggests that the motives that stimulated the creation of beadwork traditions in the different areas were different. The main function of the earliest African and Near-Eastern beadworks seems to be that of circulating in an exchange system may be to reinforce reciprocity networks ensuring the survival of hunter-gatherer groups in times of stress or to maintain long-term social bonds. In Europe and Eurasia beads seem rather to have been used to strengthen affiliation to a group and visualize social and individual roles within the group. Interestingly, the regional patterning of beadtype distribution in the European Early Upper Palaeolithic transgresses changes in lithic technology and human populations.

A Behavioral Ecology Perspective: How Much of Culture is Cultural?

James F O'Connell

Department of Anthropology, University of Utah, Salt Lake City

An answer to this question turns initially on the definition of 'culture.' As an archaeologist interested in human evolution, I define it (broadly) as hominin behavior and its material consequences. Behavioral ecology provides a theoretical framework suitable for predicting and explaining variability in these two phenomena. I provide a brief description of behavioral ecology's goals and basic operating assumptions, illustrate by example its application in ethnographic, archaeological and paleoanthropological contexts and the lessons learned as a result; then highlight some of its particular strengths and limitations in the context of archaeological research on human evolution in the late Middle and early Upper Pleistocene.

Notes for discussion: In-depth examination of the complete model of expansion of cultural capacity.

Antweiler, Christoph

Universität Bonn
Institut für Orient- und Asienwissenschaften (IOA)
Nassestr. 2, 53113 Bonn (Germany)

christoph.antweiler@uni-bonn.de

Bolus, Michael

Eberhard Karls Universität
The Role of Culture in Early Expansions of Humans
Tübingen (Germany)

michael.bolus@uni-tuebingen.de

Bruch, Angela

Research Institute Senckenberg
Paläontologie und Historische Geologie
Frankfurt (Germany)

abruch@senckenberg.de

Cep, Berrin

Institut für Ur- und Frühgeschichte und Archäologie des Mittelalters
Abt. Ältere Urgeschichte und Quartärökologie
Schloss, Burgsteige 11, 72070 Tübingen (Germany)

berrin.cep@gmx.de

Collard, Mark

Simon Fraser University
Department of Archaeology
Laboratory of Human Evolutionary Studies
Burnaby, British Columbia, V5A 1S6 (Canada)

mark.collard@sfu.ca

Conard, Nicholas

Eberhard Karls Universität
Abteilung Ältere Urgeschichte und Quartärökologie
Tübingen (Germany)

nicholas.conard@uni-tuebingen.de

Davidson, Iain

University of New England
Faculty of Arts and Sciences, School of Humanities
Armidale NSW 2351 (Australia)

iain.davidson@live.com.au

Delagnes, Anne

CNRS UMR 5199, Institut de Préhistoire et de Géologie du Quaternaire
University of Bordeaux 1
Bâtiment B18, Avenue des Facultés
33405, Talence (France)

a.delagnes@pacea.u-bordeaux1.fr

Gardner, Donald

Universität Luzern
Kultur- und Sozialanthropologisches seminar
Kasernenplatz 3, Postfach 7455
Luzern 6007 (Switzerland)

donald.gardner@unilu.ch

Goren-Inbar, Naama

Hebrew University
Institute of Archaeology
Mt. Scopus, Jerusalem 91905 (Israel)

goren@cc.huji.ac.il

Haidle, Miriam

Research Institute Senckenberg
The Role of Culture in Early Expansions of Humans
Frankfurt (Germany)

miriam.haidle@uni-tuebingen.de

Hertler, Christine

Research Institute Senckenberg
The Role of Culture in Early Expansions of Humans
Frankfurt (Germany)

c.hertler@bio.uni-frankfurt.de

Hochschild, Volker

Eberhard Karls Universität
The Role of Culture in Early Expansions of Humans
Tübingen (Germany)

hochschild@uni-tuebingen.de

- Kanaeva, Zara** zara.kanaeva@geographie.uni-tuebingen.de
Eberhard Karls Universität
The Role of Culture in Early Expansions of Humans
Tübingen (Germany)
- Kandel, Andrew** a.kandel@uni-tuebingen.de
Eberhard Karls Universität,
The Role of Culture in Early Expansions of Humans
Tübingen (Germany)
- Annette Kehnel** annette.kehnel@uni-mannheim.de
Historisches Institut
Universität Mannheim
68131 Mannheim
- Lombard, Marlize** mlombard@uj.ac.za
University of Johannesburg, Institute for Human Evolution
Department of Anthropology and Development Studies
University of the Witwatersrand, Johannesburg (South Africa)
- Maerker, Michael** michael.maerker@geographie.uni-tuebingen.de
Eberhard Karls Universität
The Role of Culture in Early Expansions of Humans
Tübingen (Germany)
- McPherron, Shannon** mcpherro@eva.mpg.de
Max Planck Institute for Evolutionary Anthropology
Department of Human Evolution
Deutscher Platz 6, 04103 Leipzig (Germany)
- Mosbrugger, Volker** volker.mosbrugger@senckenberg.de
Forschungsinstitut Senckenberg
Frankfurt (Germany)
- Müller-Beck, Hansjürgen** hansjuergen.mueller-beck@uni-tuebingen.de
Institut für Ur- und Frühgeschichte und Archäologie des Mittelalters
Abt. Ältere Urgeschichte und Quartärökologie
Schloss, Burgsteige 11, 72070 Tübingen (Germany)
- Nowell, April** anowell@uvic.ca
University of Victoria
Department of Anthropology
P.O. Box 3050, STN CSC, Victoria, BC V8W 3P5 (Canada)
- Nwokeji, Chidi** chidi.nwokeji@senckenberg.de
Research Institute Senckenberg
The Role of Culture in Early Expansions of Humans
Frankfurt (Germany)
- O'Connell, James F.** james.oconnell@anthro.utah.edu
University of Utah
Department of Anthropology
270 S. 1400 East Room 102,
Salt Lake City, UT 84112-0060 (USA)
- Schiefenhövel, Wulf** schiefen@orn.mpg.de
Max-Planck-Institute for Ornithology
Von-der-Tann-Str. 3, 82346 Andechs (Germany)
- Schmidt, Patrick** patrick.schmidt@senckenberg.de
Research Institute Senckenberg
The Role of Culture in Early Expansions of Humans
Frankfurt (Germany)
- Schrenk, Friedemann** schrenk@senckenberg.de
Research Institute Senckenberg
Paleoanthropology Section
Frankfurt (Germany)

-
- Sellin, Volker** volker.sellin@zegk.uni-heidelberg.de
Historisches Seminar der Universität Heidelberg
Grabengasse 3-5
69117 Heidelberg (Germany)
- Shennan, Stephen** s.shennan@ucl.ac.uk
UCL, Institute of Archaeology,
31-34 Gordon Sq, WC1H 0PY London (GB)
- Tennie, Claudio** tennie@eva.mpg.de
Max Planck Institute for Evolutionary Anthropology
Dept. of Developmental and Comparative Psychology
Deutscher Platz 6 04103 Leipzig (Germany)
- Uthmeier, Thorsten** thorsten.uthmeier@ufl.phil.uni-erlangen.de
Friedrich-Alexander-Universität
Institut für Ur- und Frühgeschichte
Erlangen-Nürnberg, Kochstr. 4/18, 91054 Erlangen (Germany)
- Vanhaeren, Marian** marian.vanhaeren@mae.u-paris10.fr
CNRS UMR 7041 ArScAn
Ethnologie préhistorique
21 allée de l'Université, 92023 Nanterre (France)
- Volmer, Rebekka** volmer@bio.uni-frankfurt.de
Goethe University
Institute for Ecology, Evolution and Diversity
Frankfurt (Germany)
- Wadley, Lyn** Lyn.Wadley@wits.ac.za
University of the Witwatersrand
School of Geography, Archaeology and Environmental Studies
Institute for Human Evolution, Johannesburg (South Africa)
- Whiten, Andrew** aw2@st-andrews.ac.uk
University of St Andrews
School of Psychology,
South Street, St Andrews, KY16 9JP (Scotland)
- Wolf, Sibylle** sibylle.wolf@uni-tuebingen.de
Institut für Ur- und Frühgeschichte und Archäologie des Mittelalters
Abt. Ältere Urgeschichte und Quartärökologie
Schloss, Burgsteige 11, 72070 Tübingen (Germany)